

STEREOCHEMISTRY OF 3-BROMOFLAVANONES, 3-BROMOFLAVAN-4-OLS AND FLAVAN-3:4-DIOLS

BY C. G. JOSHI AND A. B. KULKARNI

Two isomeric 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavanones have been synthesised and on the basis of conversion of one into the other and their infra-red data, conformations have been assigned to them. These bromoflavanones have further been reduced to the corresponding-3-bromoflavan-4-ols and on the basis of chemical reactions and physical data, conformations have been assigned to these bromohydrins. One of the above bromohydrins has been converted into the corresponding flavan-3:4-diol diacetate. Further, the stereochemistry of all the four racemates of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3:4-diol has been discussed and conformations assigned to them.

In a previous communication (Kulkarni and Joshi, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 1456) on the synthesis of flavan-3:4-diols the concept of conformational analysis (Barton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1027) was for the first time introduced in this field of anthoxanthins to understand their stereochemistry. Dihydropyran ring was compared with cyclohexene (Barton, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 21) and the equatorial-favoured conformation for side phenyl nucleus was suggested. The present communication discusses the stereochemistry of 3-bromoflavanones, 3-bromoflavan-4-ols and flavan-3:4-diols.

Stereochemistry of 3-Bromoflavanones

Earlier only one isomer of a 3-bromoflavanone (Zemplen and Bogner, *Ber.*, 1943, 76, 452; Seshadri *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1954, 39A, 254) was reported though theoretically two isomers having different configuration for C₃-Br can exist. Recently, Limaye and co-workers (*Rasayanam*, 1955, 2, 90) reported the isolation of two 3-bromoflavanones, but they did not discuss the theoretical implications of their existence. They further reported the conversion of the isomer (II) into its epimer (I) by boiling it with acetic acid-hydrochloric acid (85:15), but latter could not be converted into the former, thus indicating the comparative stability of the higher melting isomer. In the light of our previous hypothesis and the above observation on conversion, the stable isomer (I) is assigned a favoured (2e, 3e) conformation and its epimer (II), (2e, 3a) conformation. According to their method 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavanone (II: m.p. 138°) obtained by the cyclisation of chalcone dibromide and its isomer (I: m.p. 152°), prepared by bromination of the corresponding flavanone, were synthesised (Bhide, Ph.D. thesis, Poona University, 1953) and the observation of Limaye and co-workers on these compounds being 3-bromoflavanones was confirmed by their dehydrobromination to the corresponding flavone.

U. V. and I. R. spectroscopic studies of α -halogeno-cyclic ketones by Cookson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 282) and Jones *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 2828; cf. Corey, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 2301) have helped to assign conformation to the halogen atom. Ring B of 3-bromoflavanone may be compared with α -halogeno-cyclic ketone and, hence, comparative U. V. and I. R. spectral studies of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavanone and the two isomeric 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavanones were undertaken. U.V. spectra of the above three compounds were identical and hence were not helpful in distinguishing between axial and equatorial bromine bonds. In infra-red spectra of substituted flavans, assuming that the flavan absorption is fairly constant, a band of lower frequency 663 cm^{-1} in the infra-red curve of the lower-melting 3-bromoflavanone (II) indicates C₃-Br as axial and a band at higher frequency 752 cm^{-1} in the curve of its isomer shows it to be equatorial (Barton and Cookson *Quart. Rev.*, 1956, 10, 64). This physical evidence is in agreement with the conformations suggested to the carbonyl frequencies of the three ketones though this frequency is generally used to assign conformations to α -halogens in the cyclic ketones (Cookson and Dandegaonkar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 282).

Stereochemistry of 3-Bromoflavan-4-ols

On reduction of 6-methyl-4'-methoxybromoflavanone (II: m.p. 138°) with lithium aluminium hydride to the corresponding 3-bromoflavan-4-ol (IV: m.p. 200°) was obtained in almost quantitative yield (Kulkarni and Joshi, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1956, 124). This bromohydrin on treatment with acetic acid-potassium acetate afforded a diol diacetate (V: m.p. 152°) which was not identical with any of the two diol diacetates (Kulkarni and Joshi, *ibid.*, 1954, 1456) previously synthesised by the reduction of the dihydroflavanol with C₃-OH equatorial and which were isomeric in position "4". By exclusion this diol diacetate must have a different configuration for C₃-OH, i.e., C₃-OH must be axial. Further, on treatment with sodium hydroxide in dioxane, this 3-bromoflavan-4-ol furnished an epoxide (VI: m.p. 116°) which on treatment with acetic acid-sulphuric

acid and acetylation afforded the same diol diacetate, m.p. 152°. On the basis of the accepted mechanism (Shoppee *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4225) of the formation of the epoxide with inversion at C₃-Br bond, *i.e.* C₃-Br (a) → C₃-O (e) and its *trans*- (a, a)-opening (Shoppee and Summers, *ibid.*, 1952, 3381; Fürst and Plattner, 12th Inter. Congr. Pure & Applied Chemistry, New York, 1951, Abs. Papers, S 409; cf. Barton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1033; Fürst and Scotoni, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 36, 1410) the diol diacetate should have both C₃-OCOCH₃ and C₂-OCOCH₃ axial. This leads us to believe that 3-bromoflavan-4-ol has C₃-Br and C-OH both axial and, hence, it is assigned (2e, 3a, 4a) conformation. The bromohydrin on boiling with alcoholic hydrochloric acid develops a coloration characteristic of anthocyanidin formation. Such a behaviour would be expected of a bromohydrin with C₃-Br (a) as it would be easily dehydrobrominated by *trans*-(a, a) elimination to provide an anthocyanidin through its leucobase. This observation further supports the configuration assigned.

The above conformation is supported by the infra-red curves of 3-bromoflavan-4-ol and its acetate. Absorption bands of 3-bromoflavan-4-ol at 1038 cm⁻¹ and 995 cm⁻¹ are attributed to C₃-OH (a) and one at 623 cm⁻¹ is also due to C₃-Br (a). In its acetate bands at 1754, 1226, 1035, and 1000 cm⁻¹ are due to C₃-acetate (a) and bands at 626 and 738 are assigned to C₃-Br (a).

Similarly, on reduction of 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavanone (I) with C₃-Br (e), m.p. 152°, with lithium aluminium hydride, the corresponding 3-bromoflavan-4-ol (III) is obtained. On the basis of reduction mechanism due to hydrides, *i.e.*, in α -equatorially substituted ketone, both equatorial and axial approaches are equally favoured and therefore the reaction should be "products development controlled" (Williams *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2579 and references cited therein) and, hence, thermodynamically more stable, *i.e.*, C₃-OH (e) conformation is assigned to the reduction product. 3-Bromoflavan-4-ol would therefore have (2e, 3e, 4e) conformation (III). C₃-Br (e) of this bromohydrin [(C₃-OH (e), C₃-Br (e))] could not be replaced by an acetoxy group as was the case

with the previous one [C_3 -OH, (a) ; C_3 -Br (a)] instead it afforded flav-3-ene-4-acetate. This experimental evidence is in agreement with the observation of Alt and Barton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4287) that replacement reaction proceeds smoothly with a diaxial bromohydrin but takes a different course with the diequatorial compound and, thus, indirectly supports the conformation assigned. On boiling with alcoholic hydrochloric acid, the bromohydrin does not exhibit an anthocyanidin coloration, as would be expected of a bromohydrin with C_3 -Br (e). The bromine atom cannot be easily eliminated due to its equatorial character. These assignments to C_3 -Br and C_4 -OH are further supported by I.R. spectral analysis. Bands of this bromohydrin at 1080, 1035, 950 cm^{-1} are due to C_4 -OH (e) and bands at 760 and 667 cm^{-1} are due to C_3 -Br (e). In its acetate bands at 1748, 1230, 1070, 1030 cm^{-1} are assigned to C_4 -acetate (e) and the band at 760 cm^{-1} is assigned to C_3 -Br (e) (compare with other bromohydrin).

Stereochemistry of Flavan-3:4-diols

(A). *Flavan-3:4-diols isomeric in position "4"*:—6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3:4-diols (VIII: m. p. 169°) and its isomer (IX: m.p. 193°) having a different configuration for C_4 -OH were obtained on reduction of the corresponding dihydroflavonol [VII: C_4 -OH (e) ; Kulkarni and Joshi, *loc. cit.*, p. 1456] with lithium hydride. The lower-melting isomer was also obtained almost in quantitative yield on catalytic reduction of dihydroflavonol in acidic medium. On the basis of the generalisation that catalytic hydrogenation of an unhindered ketone in acidic medium affords an axial alcohol, C_4 -OH of the lower-melting racemate is assigned axial conformation. C_4 -OH of the other isomer is therefore equatorial. The higher-melting racemate (XIV) therefore is assigned (2e, 3e, 4e) conformation and the lower-melting one, (2e, 3e, 4a) conformation. The above conformations are further supported by the following chemical evidences and accepted generalisations.

(i). The assignments postulated comply with the Auwer-Skita rule (Von Auwers, *Annalen*, 1920, 420, 89 ; Skita, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 1792) which holds good rigidly for 1:2-derivatives of cyclohexane (Hückel, *Annalen*, 1937, 533, 1). Thus *trans*-(4e, 3e) isomer has higher melting point and lower solubility than the *cis*-(4a, 4e) isomer.

(ii). The *cis*-(3e, 4a) isomer (VIII) on treatment with ethyl chloroformate (King and Clark-Lewis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1399) forms a cyclic carbonate. Under identical experimental conditions the *trans*-(3e, 4e) is recovered unchanged. The formation of cyclic carbonate can also take place if the conformation is *cis*-(3a, 4e), but this assignment goes against the conformation assigned to the original dihydroflavonol as C_3 -OH equatorial and the chemical evidence cited under (iii).

(iii). On chromatographic elution of diol diacetates on activated alumina, the acetate of *cis*-(3e, 4a)-diol is eluted first. This sequence of elution is in agreement with the generalisation (Savard, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1953, 202, 457 ; Stoll *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 37, 1039 ; Alt and Barton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4284) that *cis* compounds are eluted out first.

(iv). The diacetate of *cis*-(3e, 4a)-diol was hydrolysed to 60.2% while that of *trans*-(3e, 4e)-diol hydrolysed to 70.0% under identical experimental conditions. C_4 -OH (a) is sterically more hindered than C_4 -OH (e) by C_3 -OH (a) and, hence, the velocity of

hydrolysis of the former should be slow, as has been experimentally observed. These data are in agreement with the conformation assigned.

(B). *The Third Racemate of the Flavan-3:4-diol.*—The diacetate of the third racemate synthesised from 3-bromo-(C₃-Br, a)-flavan-4-ol-(C₄-OH-a) is different from the two diol diacetates, isomeric in position-4, reported above. Hence, it follows by exclusion that this racemate must have a different configuration, *i. e.*, C₃-OCOCH₃ must be axial. It is therefore assigned *trans*-(C₃-OCOCH₃-a, C₄-OCOCH₃-a) conformation.

This configuration is further supported by the fact that it does not form a cyclic carbonate on hydrolysis, as would be expected of a *trans*-(a-a)-diol. This assignment suggests that C₃-Br (a) is replaced by C-OCOCH₃ (a) with retention of configuration.

Such SN¹-type mechanism for replacement of halogen has been previously observed by Shoppee *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 1147; 1955, 679, 686) and Winstein *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1140) and is explained on double bond or aromatic π -electron participation. The same diacetate (C₃-OCOCH₃-a, C₄-OCOCH₃-a) is formed by the opening of an epoxide (4a, 3e), obtained from 3-bromo-(C-Br, a) - flavan-4-ol (C₄-OH, a). This conformation is further in agreement with the well-established mechanism, for the *trans*-(a-a)-opening of an epoxide-(4a-3e) formed by inversion (Winstein and Buckle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2787) of C₃-Br-(a) to C₃-O-(e). Inversion at C₃-Br-(a) to C₃-O-(e), assumed to take place during the formation of epoxide, does not go against the explanation given above for retention of configuration, as it is well established by Winstein *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1140) and recently by Shoppee *et al.*, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 494) that in spite of the phenyl group participation, the solvent and the reagent play a very important part in deciding the halogen-replacement mechanism. The experimental conditions used for the epoxide formation are very favourable for inversion of configuration while those used for replacement of bromine are favourable for retention of configuration (cf. Winstein, *loc. cit.*).

(C). *The Fourth Racemate.*—The remaining fourth racemate (XI) would have (2e, 3a, 4e) conformation, the same assigned to synthetic melacacidin obtained by King and Clark-Lewis (*Chem. & Ind.* 1953, 1368; *loc. cit.*). This assignment of King *et al.* is complementary to our above assignments to the three racemates and is in agreement with both

the formation of cyclic carbonate from his diol and the generalisation of catalytic *cis*-addition of hydrogen to the double bond of the flavonol and formation of comparatively stable isomer.

Regarding the investigation of Bogner and Raskosi (*Chem. & Ind.*, 1956, 188) on the synthesis of flavan-3:4-diols and their isolation of only one isomer, we may add that we have further isolated both the isomers in a number of cases either by chromatography of diol diacetates or by partial crystallisation of diols, and, hence, their conclusions are not convincing.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflav-3-ene-3:4-epoxide (VI).—The bromohydrin (m.p. 200 ; 0.5 g.) was dissolved in dioxane (50 c.c.) and 10*N*-NaOH solution (5 c.c.) was added to it and heated to a gentle reflux for 4½ hours and then poured in cold water. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed thoroughly with water, dried and dissolved in petroleum ether and filtered. On removing petroleum ether a colorless residue was obtained which was crystallised twice from alcohol, m.p. 115-17°; yield 0.15 g. (Found: C, 76.1; H, 6.5. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 76.1; H, 6.0%).

Hydrolysis of the Diacetate of 6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3:4-diol (IX).—The diacetate (m.p. 98°; 10 mg.) was dissolved in alcohol and boiled with NaOH (0.01*N*; 5 c.c.) for 20 minutes. The excess of alkali was titrated against 0.01*N*-HCl. Alkali consumed was 3.9 c.c. of 0.01*N*; % hydrolysis, 72.2.

Hydrolysis of the Diacetate of 6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3:4-diol (VIII).—The diacetate (m.p. 123°; 20 mg.) was dissolved in alcohol and boiled with 0.01*N*-NaOH (10 c.c.) for 20 minutes. The excess of alkali was titrated against 0.01*N*-HCl. The alkali consumed was 6.5 c.c. of 0.01*N*; % hydrolysis, 60.2.

Cyclic Carbonate of the Diol (VIII) (m.p. 169°).—To a solution of the flavan-3:4-diol (m.p. 169°) (0.1 g.) in benzene-dioxane (6 + 1 c.c.) and ethyl chloroformate (1 c.c.) was added dropwise triethylamine (1 c.c.) when boiling commenced and a precipitate was formed. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 2 hours and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated and the residue was crystallised three times from petroleum ether, m.p. 144°, yield 0.04 g. (Found: C, 69.11; H, 4.90. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.23; H, 5.12%).

Chromatographic Separation of the Mixture of the Diol Diacetates (m.p. 123° & 98°).—6-Methyl-4'-methoxydihydroflavonol (1 g.) was reduced with $LiAlH_4$ and the residue (0.6 g.) obtained after working up the reaction mixture as usual was acetylated with acetic anhydride (4 c.c.) and pyridine (2 c.c.). The mixture of the diacetates was dissolved in minimum amount of benzene and chromatographed over activated alumina. The first two fractions eluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°; 50 c.c. each) gave a semi-solid which could not be induced to crystallise. Fractions 3 to 5, eluted out with petroleum ether-benzene (90:10), gave a crystalline substance, m.p. 98-115° (0.27 g.) which on recrystallisation furnished the diol diacetate, m.p. 123°, as the main product.

Fractions 6, 7 and 8, eluted with the same solvent, mainly consisted of the diacetate of m.p. 98°, and the diol of m.p. 193° could be isolated by its hydrolysis.

Synthesis of 6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3:4'-diol-diacetate from 6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflav-3-ene-3:4-epoxide.—To a solution of the epoxide (m.p. 115-17°) (0.15 g.) in glacial acetic acid (5 c.c.) was added H₂SO₄ (conc., 0.1 c.c.) and was allowed to stand for 5 hours. The solution was poured in water and the product extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether distilled over when an oil was obtained. The oily residue was acetylated with acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) and pyridine (1 c.c.) and worked up as usual, when a compound, m.p. 152°, was obtained (yield 0.1 g.). It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 152°; mixed m.p. with the diol diacetate, described above, showed no depression.

TABLE I

Ultraviolet and infra-red data.

Name of the compound.	Ultraviolet frequency.		Infra-red frequency.
	$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ole}}$	Log ϵ .	
6-Methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavanone (II), m.p. 138° (Limaye, <i>loc. cit.</i>).	2240Å	4.47	1696, 1610, 1585, 1515, 1474, 1200, 821 and 663 cm ⁻¹ (CS ₂)
	2610	4.01	
	3350	3.56	
6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavanone (Auwers <i>et al.</i> , <i>Ber.</i> , 1921, 84B, 1543)	2200	4.46	1685, 1610, 1588, 1515, 1470, 1224, 836, 802 cm ⁻¹ (Nujol)
	2540	4.03	
	3320	3.56	
6-Methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavanone (I), m.p. 152° (Limaye, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	2240	4.49	1692, 1610, 1585, 1515, 1474, 1200, 821, 752, 543 cm ⁻¹ (CS ₂)
	2610	4.03	
	3350	3.62	
6-Methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavan-4- ol (IV), m.p. 200° (Kulkarni & Joshi, <i>loc. cit.</i> , 1956)	...	... •	1038, 995, cm ⁻¹ (CS ₂) ; 623 (Nujol) and additional maxima due to methoxyflavan system.
Acetate (Kulkarni <i>et al.</i> , <i>loc. cit.</i>)	...	...	1754, 1226, 1035, 1000, 738, 626 cm ⁻¹ (CS ₂) and maxi- ma due to methoxyflavan system.
6-Methoxy-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavan-4-ol (III), m.p. 175° (Kulkarni & Joshi, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	...	...	760, 667 cm ⁻¹ (Nujol) and maxima due to methoxy- flavan system ; 1070, 1035, 950 cm ⁻¹ (CS ₂) in addition to the maxima due to methoxyflavan system.
	...	...	
	...	...	
Acetate (Kulkarni <i>et al.</i> , <i>loc. cit.</i>)	...	...	1748, 1230, 1070, 1030, 760 cm ⁻¹ (CS ₂) & maxima due to methoxyflavan system.
6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3:4-diol (IX), m.p. 193° (Kulkarni & Joshi, <i>loc. cit.</i> , p. 1456)	...	...	3565, 3350, 1680, 1516, 1510, 1238, 1022, 836 cm ⁻¹ (Nujol)
	...	...	
	...	...	

TABLE I (contd.)

Ultraviolet and infra-red data.

Name of the compound.	Ultraviolet frequency.		Infra-red frequency.
	$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{abs}}$	Log ϵ ,	
Diacetate (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	...	...	1742, 1612, 1516, 1510, 1238, 1031, 826 cm^{-1} (Nujol)
6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3:4-diol (VIII), m.p. 169° (Kulkarni <i>et al.</i> , <i>loc. cit.</i> , p. 1456)	...	...	3570, 3455, 3220, 1612, 1590, 1518, 1238, 1034, 1006, 831 cm^{-1} (Nujol)
Diacetate (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	...	...	1742, 1610, 1590, 1510, 1238, 1034, 1006, 831 cm^{-1} (Nujol)
6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-3:4-diol diacetate (V), m.p. 152° (Kulkarni & Joshi, <i>loc. cit.</i> , 1956)	...	...	1740, 1610, 1590, 1506, 1220, 1025, 826 cm^{-1} (Nujol)

The authors are grateful to Profs. D. H. R. Barton, F.R.S. and R. C. Shah for helpful discussion and Dr. Eglington for Infra-red curves and their interpretation.

THE NATIONAL CHEMICAL LABORATORY, POONA,
AND
DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE, BOMBAY.

Received November 22, 1956.